

SYMPTOMS OF DISEASES OF CHILDREN 7-9 YEARS OLD WITH CEREBRAL PALSY AND THEIR CAUSES

Abdumuminova Khulkar

Jizzakh State Pedagogical University, 2nd year Master of Defectology

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7188666>

This article reviews the outcomes and causes of cerebral palsy in young children. The analysis of changes resulting from the disease is also considered.

Keywords: cerebral palsy, mental retardation, psychological changes, hyperkinesia, epilepsy, neonatology, dysarthria, diagnosis, disease.

Cerebral palsy (ICP) is a general concept of movement disorders caused by changes in various brain structures in the perinatal period. Children with cerebral palsy suffer from mono-, hemi-, para-, tetraparesis and paresis, pathology of muscle tone, hyperkinesia, speech defects, impaired coordination of movements, motor and mental retardation of the child. Mental retardation, psychological changes, epilepsy and changes in hearing and vision can also develop with FBF (DSP). The disease is diagnosed based on the history and clinical symptoms. Children with DSP will have to be treated in rehabilitation centers all their lives, receive medication, and, if necessary, surgical intervention. Worldwide, ASD occurs in 1.7-7 children out of 1000. In premature babies, this figure is 10 times higher. Recent studies have shown that this pathology is observed in 40-50% of premature babies. Cerebral palsy is one of the leading problems in pediatrics. The reason for this is the deterioration of the environment, the development of the field of neonatology, the survival rate of premature babies (even children born 500 g survive), which means that the disease is widespread and relevant. Worldwide, ASD occurs in 1.7-7 children out of 1000. In premature babies, this figure is 10 times higher. Recent studies have shown that this pathology is observed in 40-50% of premature babies.

Cerebral palsy is one of the leading problems in pediatrics. The reason for this is the deterioration of the environment, the development of the field of neonatology, the survival rate of premature babies (even children born 500 g survive), which means that the disease is widespread and relevant. Causes of cerebral palsy. At present, damage to the brain under the influence of various factors, improper formation or death of nerve cells in certain areas of the brain can be called the cause of the development of DSP. The impact of these factors in the perinatal period or in a short time (up to 4 weeks) after the birth of a child increases the likelihood of developing the disease. The main factor in the development of DSP is hypoxia. Under the influence of hypoxia, the centers of the brain responsible for movement and coordination are primarily damaged.

As a result, children develop symptoms of DSP - pathology of muscle tone, paresis and paralysis.

The factors leading to the development of DSP during pregnancy are as follows:

fetoplacental insufficiency;

premature migration of the placenta;

nephropathy of pregnant women;

infections of pregnant women (cytomegalovirus, rubella, toxoplasmosis, herpes, syphilis);

Rhesus conflict;

somatic diseases of a pregnant woman (diabetes mellitus, hypothyroidism, congenital and acquired heart defects, arterial hypertension);

Various injuries of a woman during pregnancy. Classification of chipboard in children. In pediatric neurology, 5 types of DSP are distinguished depending on the area of damage to the structure of the brain. The most common among them is spastic diplegia. This is the situation in 40-80% of all CSPs.

The motor centers of the brain are affected, which leads to paresis in the legs. If only one hemisphere of the brain is affected, the movement disorder appears on the opposite side of the body. In most cases of cerebral palsy, there is a hyperkinetic form associated with damage to the subcortical centers. In the clinic of the disease, involuntary movements are manifested - hyperkinesia, and this condition manifests itself when the child is excited and afraid. Atonic-astatic cerebral palsy is formed as a result of damage to the cerebellum. Symptoms of the disease are manifested in the form of static and coordination, muscle atony. The most severe manifestation of DSP is bilateral hemiplegia. In this case, there is a bilateral lesion of the cerebral hemispheres. Due to muscle rigidity, it is difficult for children not only to walk, stand straight, but also to hold their heads on their own. Symptoms of cerebral palsy in children

Cerebral palsy in children occurs in many forms and with varying degrees of severity. The clinical symptoms of the disease depend on the affected area and the depth of the brain structure. Sometimes the symptoms of cerebral palsy appear immediately after the birth of the child. Often, the disease is detected after a few months with a lag in the physical development of the child on examination by a pediatrician. The main clinical symptom of DSP is the inability of children to perform new range of motion movements and learn new skills. A child with cerebral palsy cannot hold his head for a long time, is not interested in toys, cannot turn his head, cannot move his arms and legs freely, and cannot take toys. If the child is held by the hand and the feet are pulled to the ground, he

does not stand completely with the soles of the feet, only the tips of the feet touch the ground. DSP can be manifested by unilateral or bilateral paresis. If the speech center is affected, the child develops symptoms of speech disorders (dysarthria). With the defeat of the centers that control swallowing and the activity of the larynx, there are problems with swallowing (dysphagia). Muscle tone is increased in all forms of DSP. Movements in the limbs are limited, movements in the joints are lost, as a result, the muscles of the limbs atrophy and become disproportionate in relation to the body. Children with cerebral palsy have specific deformations of the body structure (scoliosis, chest deformities). Movement disorders and skeletal deformities cause chronic pain in children. Pain appears in the neck, shoulders, back. Cerebral palsy in hyperkinetic form is characterized by sudden symptoms: repeated turns of the head to one side, appearance of the face, tremor, repetition of the same movements. With atonic-astatic DSP, the impossibility of maintaining balance when walking, muscle weakness, falls, and tremor are noted. In addition to the above symptoms, children with cerebral palsy may have other pathologies, such as malaise, changes in the gastrointestinal system, breathing problems, urinary incontinence. About 20-40% of ASDs are accompanied by epilepsy. About 60% of children with CPD have vision problems. Some patients also experience deafness or hearing loss. Mentally, children may also have delays in development, perception and concentration, learning difficulties and behavioral abnormalities.

Despite the fact that DSP is chronic, the disease does not progress, on the contrary, the symptoms gradually decrease as the child grows and develops. Patients may suffer from secondary conditions such as epilepsy, stroke, cerebral hemorrhage, or more severe physical illness.

Chipboard diagnostics

There are no specific criteria for diagnosing cerebral palsy.

However, as soon as the baby is born, several indicators indicate that the baby may develop DSP, including: a low Agar score, abnormal range of motion, impaired muscle tone, and physical and mental retardation of the baby. . If such conditions are detected in a child, a pediatric neurologist should examine him and conduct a series of tests. Checks include: electroencephalography (EEG);

electrotomography;

electroneurography;

Transcranial magnetic stimulation.

In addition to the above symptoms, children with cerebral palsy may have other pathologies, such as malaise, changes in the gastrointestinal system, breathing problems, urinary incontinence. About 20-40% of ASDs are accompanied by epilepsy. About 60% of children with CPD have vision problems. Some patients also experience deafness or hearing loss. Mentally, children may also have delays in development, perception and concentration, learning difficulties and behavioral abnormalities.

References:

1. Abdurakhmonov, Zh. U. Study of the pharmaceutical market of Uzbekistan and the prospects for its development / Zh. U. Abdurakhmonov, O. M. Voronina // Topical issues in the development of new drugs: abstracts of the XXIV international scientific and practical conference of young scientists and students, 20 April 2017 - X., 2017. - Issue. 2. - S. 193-194.
2. VITON (2019). Pharmaceutical market of Uzbekistan. [online] Slideshare.net. Available at: <https://www.slideshare.net/vaytonbrandcapital/pharmaceutical-market-of-uzbekistan> [Accessed October 14, 2019].
3. Akihiro Hashimoto, Shoko Haneda Measuring changes in Japanese R&D performance pharmaceutical industry / Research Policy 37 (2008) 1829–1836
4. Honjo, Y., Haneda, S.: Assessing the research and development of Japanese pharmaceutical firms using DEA. J.Sci. Policy Res. Management 13, 96–105 (1998).

